

Systematic review of teaching methods in language education: trends and innovation

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ABSTRACT

This systematic literature review (SLR) examines the developing pedagogical methods in language instruction, emphasizing modern practices, technological advancements, and cultural diversity. The research seeks to fill significant gaps in the literature by examining effective pedagogical strategies that improve language acquisition results. In accordance with the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) methodology, a systematic search of the Scopus and Web of Science (WoS) databases was performed, focusing on publications published from 2022 to 2024. 30 primary studies were examined through topic synthesis and integrative analysis. The findings are categorized into three themes: i) contextualized and adaptive teaching methods in language education: balancing traditional approach and innovation; ii) impact of innovative teaching on language learning: technology and student engagement; and iii) cultural diversity's impact on language education and engagement. The results underscore the imperative of modifying teaching strategies according to different situations and incorporating technology to enhance engagement and results. Furthermore, culturally sensitive techniques were demonstrated to improve inclusivity in multilingual classrooms. These insights are pertinent to academic and professional settings, indicating widespread significance for enhancing communication and cross-cultural skills. Future research should investigate the long-term effects of these initiatives and ensure equal access to educational resources and teacher training.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Language education plays a vital role in shaping individuals' cognitive, social, and cultural development [1]–[3]. In an increasingly interconnected world, proficiency in multiple languages has become essential for personal growth, professional success, and adapting to globalized societies. Despite significant advancements in language pedagogy, concerns remain, particularly regarding essay writing skills in primary education. Many students struggle to develop effective writing abilities in their native languages, raising questions about the relevance of traditional essay teaching methods [4]. Over time, the field of language education has witnessed a paradigm shift from teacher-centered, rote-based methods to more interactive,

student-centered approaches. While effective in teaching grammar and vocabulary, traditional techniques such as the grammar-translation method have often been criticized for neglecting students' ability to use language in real-world contexts [5]. As language education evolves, newer methodologies like communicative language teaching (CLT), task-based learning (TBL), and hybrid learning models are being explored to meet the diverse needs of modern learners [6]–[8]. These methodologies focus on enhancing practical language skills, which are crucial for both personal and professional communication in today's globalized world.

The declining ability of students to write essays proficiently suggests that older methods may no longer be effective. Furthermore, teaching approaches, particularly in writing, have evolved. Still, it remains unclear whether these newer strategies fully address today's learners' diverse and complex needs. The rise of digital tools and diverse student populations has also created new challenges, requiring teaching methods that are both adaptive and culturally sensitive [9]. The digital era has further compounded the issue as students increasingly engage with technology in their learning environments [10], [11]. While digital tools such as online writing platforms, virtual classrooms, and AI-driven language programs like ChatGPT provide flexible learning opportunities, they also raise questions about the balance between technology and traditional pedagogical approaches. It is crucial to understand how these tools can be effectively integrated into language education to enhance learning without undermining essential human elements in teaching.

Moreover, cultural diversity in the classroom has introduced another layer of complexity. Students come from various linguistic backgrounds, which requires teaching methods that focus on language mechanics and engage students emotionally and socially within their cultural context [12]. This study seeks to address these gaps by conducting a systematic review of modern teaching approaches in language education. By focusing on the adaptation of teaching methods to diverse contexts, the integration of innovative pedagogical techniques, and the role of cultural diversity, this study aims to provide valuable insights into enhancing language acquisition and improving educational outcomes. Specifically, this research will examine how recent technological advancements, such as hybrid learning and digital tools, can improve language instruction. Additionally, the study will explore the impact of culturally responsive teaching practices on student engagement and writing skills, drawing on recent empirical studies from both Western and non-Western contexts. For example, Karakose *et al.* [13] highlighted the role of digital technology in education, while Castillo-Cuesta [14] examined the benefits of game-based learning in language acquisition. These and other recent studies will help contextualize the findings and contribute to the growing body of research on innovative language teaching methods.

By evaluating the integration of digital tools and culturally responsive methods in language education, this study aims to bridge the gap between traditional and modern techniques. Furthermore, it explores how these innovative strategies can help address specific challenges faced by today's educators, including the need to cater to diverse linguistic backgrounds and different learning preferences. The findings of this study are expected to provide a comprehensive overview of the effectiveness of different approaches and offer guidance for educators looking to enhance their teaching practices in response to the growing diversity and technological advancement in educational settings. To guide this investigation, the following research questions are posed:

- How does adapting teaching methods to diverse contexts enhance language acquisition?
- How do innovative teaching methods enhance language learning outcomes?
- How does cultural diversity impact language learning?

This study explores language education through a contemporary lens, integrating modern theoretical frameworks that address the real-world challenges of today's diverse and digital learning environments. The framework proposed here draws on three main concepts: digital-aided learning, culturally responsive pedagogy, and dynamic student engagement. These concepts reflect the need for teaching methods that are flexible, inclusive, and grounded in empirical research. The increasing integration of digital tools in education, such as AI-driven platforms and virtual learning environments, is transforming how languages are taught. Several studies [13], [14] emphasize the role of technology in enhancing student engagement and providing personalized learning experiences. This framework builds on connectivism but emphasizes learner autonomy, enabling students to take charge of their language learning through digital resources.

Drawing from sociocultural theory, this framework acknowledges the importance of incorporating students' cultural and linguistic backgrounds into the learning process. Previous research [15], [16] shows that culturally relevant content improves student engagement and language acquisition. Using teaching methods that connect with students' own experiences, educators can foster a more inclusive and effective learning environment. This aspect integrates transformative learning theory, focusing on active learning through critical reflection and real-world problem-solving [17]. Empirical studies, such as those by Ganapathy *et al.* [18], demonstrate the effectiveness of project-based learning (PBL) and collaborative activities in improving language skills. This concept supports the idea that active, student-centered methods improve educational outcomes, particularly in diverse classroom settings [19].

The proposed framework is grounded in empirical studies that demonstrate the effectiveness of modern teaching approaches in enhancing language acquisition [20], [21]. By integrating digital tools and culturally relevant pedagogy, this model addresses both the technological advancements and the increasing diversity seen in today's classrooms. It provides practical solutions for educators to improve language learning outcomes, making it highly relevant to the current educational landscape limitations of past theories. It also offers a comprehensive approach that prioritizes engagement, diversity, and modern learning tools [22], [23]. The result is a framework designed to equip educators with practical strategies for improving language learning outcomes in diverse and technologically advanced classrooms.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This study employed the preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (PRISMA) framework to guide the systematic review process. This study was examined through topic synthesis and integrative analysis. This process allowed for a structured approach to identifying, evaluating, and selecting relevant literature aligned with the study's objectives [24]. The PRISMA methodology is particularly suited to address the research questions:

- How does adapting teaching methods to diverse contexts enhance language acquisition?
- How do innovative teaching methods enhance language learning outcomes?
- How does cultural diversity impact language learning?

These questions are addressed by exploring relevant literature through the systematic review process. The methodological steps included identification, screening, eligibility, and final inclusion.

2.1. Identification

To conduct a thorough identification of relevant literature, search strings were developed using key terms related to teaching approaches, language education, and writing. Table 1 presents that these search strings were applied to two major academic databases, Scopus and Web of Science (WoS), to retrieve studies from 2022 to 2024. In addition to the primary keywords, dictionaries, thesauri, encyclopedias, and previous studies were consulted to refine the search terms further. A total of 2,101 papers were initially retrieved using the following search strings, ensuring a broad scope of potentially relevant studies.

Table 1. The search string

Category	Keywords
Scopus	TITLE-ABS-KEY (teaching AND approach AND language AND education AND writing) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2022) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2023) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR, 2024)) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "SOC") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "ARTS")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) Date of access: Jun 2024
WoS	Teaching AND approach AND language AND education AND writing (Topic) and 2024 or 2023 or 2022 (Publication Years) and Article (Document Types) and English (Languages) and Article (Document Types) and Arts Humanities Other Topics or Social Sciences Other Topics (Research Areas) Date of access: Jun 2024

2.2. Screening

The screening phase attempted to assess the relevance of the discovered studies according to specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Studies were initially evaluated by their titles and abstracts, concentrating on those that directly discussed the application of pedagogical methods in language education. Throughout this procedure, superfluous or duplicate articles were eliminated. Table 2 defines the more rigorous inclusion and exclusion criteria implemented during the second screening phase. The criteria restricted the study to journal papers published from 2022 to 2024, authored in English, and concentrated on the social sciences and arts humanities disciplines. After the second screening stage, 156 papers remained, following the exclusion of 124 publications that failed to match the criteria. Two supplementary elements have been removed due to duplication.

Table 2. The selection criterion is searching

Criterion	Inclusion	Exclusion
Language	English	Non-English
Timeline	2022–2024	<2022
Literature type	Journal (Article)	Conference, book, review
Publication stage	Final	In press
Subject	Social science and art humanities	Besides social science and art humanities

2.3. Eligibility

A total of 154 articles were gathered during the third step, referred to as the eligibility evaluation. During this phase, a comprehensive examination of the titles and content of each article was conducted to confirm that they met the inclusion criteria and were relevant to the research objectives of the ongoing study. A total of 124 publications, articles, and data were excluded due to their lack of relevance to the subject, insufficient alignment with the study's objective in terms of title and abstract, and absence of empirical data to support their full-text access. Therefore, 30 papers are remaining for the next evaluation.

2.4. Data extraction and analysis

This study employed an integrative analysis approach to evaluate and synthesize diverse research methodologies, predominantly using synthesis and integrative analysis methods. This analysis aimed to identify key themes and subcategories relevant to teaching approaches in language education. The data extraction process began with a comprehensive review of the selected studies, followed by categorization based on the identified research objectives. Figure 1 illustrates the PRISMA flowchart, which outlines the systematic review process, from initial identification to the final selection of studies for analysis. In this review, three main themes emerged: i) contextualized and adaptive teaching methods in language education: balancing traditional approaches and innovation; ii) impact of innovative teaching on language learning: technology and student engagement; and iii) cultural diversity's impact on language education and engagement. Each theme was explored in detail, providing a structured framework for analysis.

To ensure consistency in the thematic development, a collaborative approach was taken. The authors worked together to analyse the data and identify common themes. During this process, a log was maintained to record observations, analysis decisions, and any emerging insights. Regular discussions were held among the authors to address discrepancies or differing interpretations, with final decisions reached through consensus. To validate the findings further, two experts specializing in language acquisition teaching methods were consulted. These experts reviewed the identified themes and provided feedback, which led to slight adjustments in the categorization process. The expert review process confirmed the validity of the identified sub-themes, ensuring that they were relevant, clear, and sufficiently comprehensive to address the research questions. Any discrepancies identified during the data analysis were addressed through comparative analysis, where the findings were cross-checked among the authors and experts. This iterative process of discussion and refinement ensured that the final themes were robust and aligned with the study's goals. The authors made revisions based on expert feedback to improve clarity and ensure the accuracy of the analysis. This systematic and collaborative approach to data extraction and analysis ensures the credibility and transparency of the study's findings, providing valuable insights into the most effective teaching practices in language education.

Figure 1. PRISMA flow diagram for systematic review

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents a thorough review of the findings regarding the three main research questions. The findings are examined in relation to the literature study and are graphically supported by tables and figures, which clarify the key trends and patterns observed.

3.1. Contextualized and adaptive teaching methods in language education: balancing traditional approaches and innovation

This section discusses how the adaptation of teaching methods to varied circumstances improves language acquisition. Examining the papers in Table 3 presents that adapting instructional strategies to particular educational contexts significantly enhances student engagement and language acquisition. Study by Bowen *et al.* [25] demonstrate that the equilibrium of language and content factors in Thai institutions resulted in enhanced English writing proficiency. Taylor [26] underscores a reductionist methodology in language arts, suggesting that material simplification mitigates teachers' stress, thereby enhancing educational efficacy. Furthermore, Peungcharoenkun and Waluyo [27] highlights the beneficial effects of combining technology with conventional approaches. In conjunction with technology, the process-genre method enhances task performance and enriches students' lexical resources. These findings confirm that varied educational environments necessitate flexible teaching methods that integrate conventional strategies with new practices. The findings indicate that adaptive teaching methods can improve language learning; however, it is crucial to acknowledge that these results may not be universally relevant in all educational contexts. The cultural and demographic backgrounds of the studies, especially those undertaken in Thailand and Malaysia, underscore the distinct demands of students in these areas. The variability of classrooms across many demographics and regions necessitates a cautious approach to the generalizability of these findings. Additional study is necessary to corroborate these methodologies across various educational settings.

Table 3. Research articles related to theme 1 based on the proposed search criteria

No	Study	Title	Year
1	[25]	The challenge of teaching English writing in Thailand: a tri-ethnography of Thai University lecturers	2023
2	[26]	A reductionist approach in curricular planning for teaching language arts	2022
3	[28]	Teacher beliefs about instructional approaches: Interrogating the notion of teaching methods	2024
4	[29]	A survey of research into English teaching approaches and instructional media in Thailand	2023
5	[27]	Implementing process-genre approach, feedback, and technology in L2 writing in higher education	2023
6	[30]	Developing Thai EFL pre-service teachers' writing skills by using the gradual release model and scaffolding approach	2024
7	[31]	Introducing peacebuilding philosophy to language teacher education	2024
8	[32]	Pre-service English teachers' understanding of preparing to teach reading skills in secondary schools	2022
9	[33]	Discourse competence as an essential variable in developing grade 11 English first additional language learners' writing skills	2023
10	[34]	Cognitive linguistics: fostering English language proficiency in higher education	2024
11	[35]	Quality education through writing: aligning learning objectives in learning materials and question papers using Bloom's taxonomy	2024
12	[36]	Collaborative literary reasoning as a support for pre-service English language arts teachers' learning about disciplinary literacy	2022
13	[37]	Investigation of language teacher's identity experiences in adopting the 'participatory' approach through active learning spaces in undergraduate education writing classrooms	2023

The results indicate that successful language education is a dynamic process necessitating the adjustment of teaching tactics to accommodate varied learner demands and settings. While fundamental, conventional approaches like the grammar-translation method are less efficacious in contemporary, dynamic language-learning contexts. This is apparent in the transition to post method and technology-integrated methodologies [27], [28]. The integration of technology with traditional techniques, as evidenced by numerous research, markedly enhances student performance in writing proficiency, task execution, and topic understanding. The research offers practical relevance to educators and policymakers by elucidating how adaptive teaching practices might mitigate the problems encountered by contemporary language learners. This study enhances the discourse on advancing language learning in many educational contexts through the integration of culturally sensitive techniques, technology, and contextualized instruction. Furthermore, the results emphasize the necessity for teacher training programs to concentrate on providing educators with competencies that enable them to reconcile conventional and progressive teaching methods.

This study's academic contribution is its thorough examination of various teaching approaches and their relevance in different cultural situations. It underscores the need for adaptability in pedagogical strategies and advocates for the investigation of hybrid methodologies that utilize technology to enhance educational results. Although the results are encouraging, some limits must be noted. The evaluated research was predominantly conducted in certain geographical areas, so the findings may not comprehensively reflect

the challenges and possibilities present in different educational contexts. Moreover, although technology integration demonstrates promise, the digital divide constitutes a substantial obstacle to its extensive implementation. Educators in under-resourced regions may find it challenging to execute these strategies effectively. Hence, future studies should investigate the adaptation of these approaches for varied classroom settings, especially those with restricted access to technical resources.

3.2. Impact of innovative teaching on language learning: technology and student engagement

The findings from the articles in Table 4 provide strong proof that innovative teaching approaches, especially those using technology, significantly improve language learning outcomes. Hudriati *et al.* [38] have shown that hybrid learning environments, integrating online and face-to-face instruction, enable educators to provide adaptable teaching methodologies. This enhanced English language proficiency, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, when conventional in-person techniques were limited. Castillo-Cuesta [39] highlighted that game-based learning enhanced English as a foreign language (EFL) writing skills, demonstrating that interactive learning methods elevate student enthusiasm and engagement. The improvements in technology, including machine learning (ML) and natural language processing (NLP), as examined by Wulff *et al.* [40], illustrate the promise of technological innovations in improving writing analytics. Their research indicated that ML and NLP enhanced educators' comprehension of students' cognitive processes, thus improving writing assessment and promoting critical thinking skills. The findings immediately respond to the research question, demonstrating that innovative teaching techniques, particularly those incorporating technology, improve learning outcomes by rendering education more engaging, personalized, and attuned to individual needs.

Previous study [38] investigated higher education in Indonesia, whereas Castillo-Cuesta [39] performed a study among university students in Ecuador. The diversity of educational contexts, student populations, and technological resources may restrict the generalizability of these findings to other areas or educational frameworks. Subsequent research should aim to replicate these novel methodologies in various contexts to assess their wider applicability. The research in theme 2 indicates that new pedagogical approaches, especially those using technology, substantially improve language learning outcomes. Hybrid learning methods, as illustrated by Hudriati *et al.* [38], provide enhanced flexibility and adaptability to the requirements of both students and institutions, especially during disruptive events such as the COVID-19 pandemic. Castillo-Cuesta [39] exemplifies the efficacy of game-based learning in enhancing language abilities through interactive and engaging techniques. The favorable response of students to game-based learning highlights its potential for wider application in various language learning environments.

Alongside hybrid and game-based learning, integrating sophisticated analytical techniques like ML and NLP, as examined by Wulff *et al.* [40], offers novel prospects for improving language education. These instruments enable educators to customize their feedback for each student, enhancing writing quality and critical thinking skills. The capacity to assess cognitive processes in real-time enhances educational adaptability, facilitating more individualized learning experiences. The research holds practical significance for both scholars and practitioners. These findings underscore the necessity for educators to incorporate technology into language instruction to improve learning outcomes. Innovative pedagogical techniques, including hybrid learning and gamified strategies, enhance student engagement and motivation, resulting in greater proficiency in language skills such as writing and reading comprehension. The research underscores the necessity for policymakers and school administrators to invest in technology infrastructure and professional development to adequately prepare teachers to implement these strategies effectively.

Notwithstanding the favorable outcomes, there remain obstacles to incorporating technology in language instruction. A significant concern is the digital gap, which restricts access to technical tools for kids from disadvantaged backgrounds. This disparity may intensify pre-existing inequalities in language learning opportunities and outcomes, hindering the attainment of equitable results. The swift progression of technological innovations necessitates ongoing professional development for educators to remain abreast of the latest tools and methods. In the absence of adequate training, educators may find it challenging to properly integrate modern technologies into their instructional methods. This study demonstrated that creative teaching approaches positively influenced language learning outcomes; nonetheless, it is essential to recognize specific limitations. The applicability of the findings may be limited by the particular cultural and geographical circumstances of the evaluated studies. Moreover, the dependence on technology presupposes that students possess the requisite digital tools, which is not invariably true, especially in under-resourced areas. These aspects must be considered while analyzing and extrapolating the results to different educational contexts. Subsequent research ought to investigate the adaptation of these strategies for various situations and assess the enduring effects of technological integration on language acquisition.

Table 4. Research articles related to theme 2 based on the proposed search area

No	Study	Title	Year
1	[38]	Hybrid learning in new normal times: shedding light on the current teaching practices towards second language acquisition in higher education context	2023
2	[39]	Using genially games for enhancing EFL reading and writing skills in online education	2022
3	[40]	Enhancing writing analytics in science education research with ML and NLP—Formative assessment of science and non-science pre-service teachers' written reflections	2023
4	[41]	The effect of analytic text-based writing strategies on ESL argumentative writing among Malaysian form-six students in Sabah, Malaysia	2023
5	[42]	Using scaffolding academic literacy practices in tertiary classrooms: a South African case study	2022
6	[43]	Corpus-based teaching of English conversation and potential integration of conversation analysis (CA) for the benefit of EFL teachers and learners	2024

3.3. Cultural diversity's impact on language education and engagement

Table 5 presents a strong correlation between cultural diversity and improved language learning outcomes. Kelly [44] has shown that integrating critical literacy into the curriculum promotes students' critical reflection on their social contexts, enhancing active engagement and a profound understanding of systematic oppression. This culturally responsive pedagogy facilitates deeper connections between students and the curriculum while fostering social fairness within the classroom. This finding unequivocally supports the research question by demonstrating that the acceptance of cultural diversity within pedagogical frameworks enhances student engagement and learning outcomes. On the other hand, Ahmed [15] underscores the necessity of equilibrating cognitive and emotional dimensions in second language writing, particularly within culturally diverse classes. His study demonstrates that students' linguistic and cultural backgrounds profoundly influence their learning experiences, and by addressing these factors, language training can be rendered more effective. This immediately addresses the research issue by illustrating how cultural variety influences and enriches language learning experiences.

The implementation of culturally responsive techniques, such as PBL, incorporates local cultural themes, as examined by Garim *et al.* [16], highlights the beneficial effects of integrating cultural contexts into language instruction. These tactics cultivate profound linkages between students' linguistic competencies and cultural backgrounds, yielding more significant learning outcomes. This validates the importance of tailoring pedagogical approaches to align with students' cultural backgrounds, as indicated by the research question. The studies underscore the advantages of culturally responsive teaching; however, the applicability of these findings is limited to specific contexts. Numerous studies were performed in distinct cultural contexts, including Kelly [44] examination of white English educators in the US and Soliman and Khalil [45] research on Arabic language teaching in the UK. These particular contexts restrict the direct transfer of findings to alternative educational settings, especially where linguistic diversity manifests in many forms. Subsequent studies should endeavor to replicate these methodologies across many cultural contexts to enhance comprehension of their wider usefulness.

The research examined in theme 3 reveals that incorporating cultural variety into language teaching boosts student engagement and improves learning outcomes. Previous research [15], [44] highlights the significance of critical language awareness and effective teaching methodologies in meeting diverse classrooms' cognitive and emotional requirements. This indicates that embracing cultural variety is essential for establishing inclusive and successful learning settings. Previous research [16], [18] substantiate the notion that PBL and genre pedagogy, when tailored to local cultural contexts, can enhance creativity and elevate writing skills, especially among indigenous or marginalized groups. This underscores the significance of culturally responsive pedagogy in guaranteeing that all students, irrespective of their background, receive high-quality language teaching. The difficulties of instructing linguistically varied groups, as highlighted by Soliman and Khalil [45] in the UK context, underscore the necessity for continuous professional development for educators. Educators must possess the resources and methodologies to adeptly navigate and incorporate cultural diversity inside their classrooms. Inadequate training may impede teachers' ability to provide linguistically and culturally suitable education, potentially obstructing student achievement. This research offers substantial benefits to both academic and practical domains by elucidating the influence of cultural variety on language acquisition. The findings underscore the necessity for practitioners to implement culturally responsive teaching methods that actively connect with students' linguistic and cultural backgrounds. This study contributes to the expanding research on cultural diversity in education, highlighting its significance for establishing equitable and successful language learning environments.

Notwithstanding the encouraging outcomes, this research has limits, especially regarding the generalizability of the data. The research was performed in particular cultural and geographical circumstances, which may not be relevant to all language acquisition settings. The study by Soliman and Khalil [45] on Arabic education in the UK may not be applicable to classrooms with varying cultural dynamics. Moreover, in certain instances, the dependence on single-class research constrains the capacity to

generalize the results over wider demographics [46]. The findings demonstrate that including cultural variety in language teaching markedly improves language learning performance. Nonetheless, the study's conclusions are constrained by contextual restrictions. The efficacy of culturally responsive teaching practices may fluctuate based on the learners' cultural, geographical, and socioeconomic contexts. Additional research is required to investigate the adaptation of these methods to various contexts and demographics. The swift demographic shifts in numerous educational settings require continuous investigation into the optimal integration of ethnic diversity in language education.

Table 5. Research articles related to theme 3 based on the proposed search criteria

No	Study	Title	Year
1	[44]	“What they allow us to learn”: exploring how white English teachers cultivate students’ critical literacies through curriculum and pedagogy	2023
2	[15]	Mapping the intersections of critical language awareness and affective approaches to second language writing	2023
3	[16]	Writing with cultural insight: elevating analytical exposition through local culture and PBL	2023
4	[18]	Creativity via a genre pedagogy to promote EFL indigenous students' writing	2022
5	[45]	The teaching of Arabic as a community language in the UK	2022
6	[47]	The impacts of Lughati for smart education initiative on students’ acquisition of Arabic language skills at the kindergarten stage	2023
7	[48]	Teachers’ perspectives and related classroom practices in mother tongue literacy development in Uganda	2023
8	[12]	ESL classroom interactions in a translanguaging space	2023
9	[32]	Pre-service English teachers’ understanding of preparing to teach reading skills in secondary schools	2022
10	[49]	Scaffolding genre-based writing in the subjects: lecturers’ learning processes in a design-based research project	2022
11	[50]	The effects of instructional scaffolding on the writing skill of English major students	2023

4. CONCLUSION

This systematic literature review (SLR) comprehensively analyses the effects of contextualized and flexible teaching approaches, innovative technology integration, and cultural diversity on language instruction. The investigation of the initial study question revealed that modifying teaching methods to suit multiple contexts markedly improves language acquisition by enabling customized training that addresses the distinct demands of students in different educational settings. This was particularly apparent in research highlighting the efficacy of approaches like the gradual release of responsibility model and technology-enhanced feedback systems. The evaluation highlighted the significance of novel pedagogical methods, including hybrid learning and game-based strategies, in improving student engagement and educational outcomes for the second study question. These strategies enhance students' linguistic abilities and motivation to engage in language learning activities, as demonstrated by other research in higher education settings. The third research topic, which investigates the influence of cultural variety, demonstrated that incorporating language and cultural diversity in classrooms promotes a more inclusive educational atmosphere. Culturally sensitive pedagogical approaches, including PBL and genre pedagogy, have been demonstrated to enhance student engagement and comprehension, especially among students from marginalized or indigenous backgrounds.

These findings enhance both academic and practical domains by providing valuable insights into optimizing language instruction through adaptability, technology integration, and cultural awareness. For academicians, the study offers a theoretical framework for future research, particularly in exploring how modern pedagogical methods can be applied to various educational contexts and investigating their long-term impact on student performance. The study also opens new avenues for research on the intersection of technology, culture, and language education, which can inform the development of more comprehensive teaching strategies. For practitioners, the evidence provided in this review is highly actionable, allowing educators to apply these methods in classroom settings to better meet the needs of diverse learners. The findings indicate that educators can leverage these techniques not only in conventional coursework but also in specialized learning environments, enhancing student achievements and engagement in language learning. By synchronizing pedagogical methods with technological innovations and cultural consciousness, educational institutions can better equip students for success in a globalized environment. However, challenges remain, including the need to ensure equitable access to technology and to provide teachers with sufficient professional development opportunities to implement these strategies effectively. Future research needs to investigate the long-term effects of these innovations and tackle these challenges to optimize the benefits of these pedagogical advances for both learners and educators.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

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I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

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Authors state no conflict of interest.

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This study does not require informed consent as no personal data or individual information was used

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study does not require ethical approval as it does not involve humans or animals

DATA AVAILABILITY

This study is a systematic literature review and does not involve the collection of primary data.

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